

CYBERBULLYING: A DANGEROUS DIGITAL PHENOMENON AND ITS PREVENTION

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Annotation: This article is dedicated to the essence of cyberbullying as a dangerous digital phenomenon, its causes, and consequences. The negative impact of cyberbullying on youth and society, including its effects on psychology, social relationships, and information security, is examined. The article analyzes practical preventive measures to combat and prevent cyberbullying, including legislative actions, educational initiatives, enhancing digital culture, and ensuring safety on social networks. Additionally, the importance of collaboration among government institutions, educational establishments, and the public in effectively countering cyberbullying is emphasized.

Keywords: Cyberbullying, digital threat, internet safety, psychology, youth, online environment, prevention, cyberethics, social networks, legislation, education, information security, cyberthreat, digital culture, victim.

In recent years, as digital technologies have become an integral part of society's life, the number of offenses committed through them has also increased. One of such serious problems is cyberbullying, that is, the implementation of actions that exert psychological pressure, threats, insults, or harassment against a person through the Internet and information and communication means.

Cyberbullying is especially widespread among adolescents and young people, posing risks to their mental health, social adaptation, and even life. This article analyzes the causes, consequences of cyberbullying, and effective preventive measures for its prevention.

Before conducting a detailed analysis of the essence and forms of expression of cyberbullying, it is advisable to first reveal the scientific and practical meaning of the term "bullying." Because cyberbullying manifests itself as one of the complex and dangerous manifestations of the phenomenon of bullying in the digital environment.

Bullying (from the English word bullying, bully - quarrelsome, bully, irritating, rude, violent) is a repeated act of various types of violence and humiliation, described above, by one person against another person who is unable to defend himself[1].

To fully understand the concept of bullying, it is necessary to highlight its important distinguishing features. Ordinary arguments, mutual disputes, or playful provocations are not characteristic of bullying. Because bullying is a set of aggressive actions that are constantly repeated, targeted, and influential, aimed at inflicting psychological, physical, or social harm on the victim, intimidating, humiliating, depressing, and subjugating them.

Bullying often occurs in educational institutions, particularly among youth and adolescents. This situation is frequently manifested in older or physically stronger students displaying aggression towards younger, weaker peers. Similar situations can be observed in workplaces, where employees may be systematically subjected to pressure and threats from

management or colleagues. Bullying can also occur within families, for example, through consistently humiliating, punishing, or comparing a child to other family members.

Cyberbullying is a type of violence that can take the following forms:

offensive correspondence (for example, insulting messages on social networks or messaging apps);

humiliation through photographs and videos;

discrediting a person through fake accounts;

threats and harassment via the internet;

dissemination of personal information.

Several factors contribute to the emergence of cyberbullying, including:

possibility of anonymity - the aggressor acts without fear of being identified;

lack of supervision - parents and school administration cannot fully monitor online activities;

lack of empathy - the level of perceiving the person behind the screen as a real individual is low;

decline in upbringing and moral values.

Cyberbullying has serious consequences for the victim:

mental health issues, depression, anxiety, and suicidal tendencies;

feelings of social isolation and distrust;

dropping out of school or educational institution;

increasing aggression towards oneself and others.

If the legal awareness and moral education of the future generation are not formed at a high level, the exacerbation of such problems as bullying and cyberbullying in society is inevitable. Therefore, it is urgent to strengthen systematic preventive and explanatory work in educational institutions to prevent these negative situations and eliminate the causes of their occurrence. In this regard, first of all, it is necessary to provide students with clear and understandable information about the essence of the concepts of bullying and cyberbullying, the harm that can be caused by them, as well as the measures of responsibility established for such actions.

At the same time, young people should be provided with practical recommendations on what actions to take to avoid these situations, what approach to adopt, and how to protect themselves psychologically. The effectiveness of such measures is ensured only through close cooperation between teachers and mentors, as well as parents, a coordinated approach, and a responsible attitude of all participants.

In Uzbekistan, the issues of ensuring the rights of children, protecting their honor and dignity are defined as one of the priority areas of state policy. In this regard, our country, guided by the international norms of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, is implementing a number of measures aimed at protecting children not only in the education system, but also in the family environment, raising their legal awareness.

The relevance of this issue was especially emphasized in the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis on December 29, 2020: "In general, in the development of any society, the healthy and harmonious upbringing of the younger generation, ensuring its future, plays a decisive role. Therefore, in further increasing the scale and effectiveness of our reforms, we rely on our comprehensively developed, ambitious, and proactive youth who have mastered modern knowledge and skills"[2].

This means that the future of the country is inextricably linked with the intellectual, spiritual, and legal potential of the younger generation. Therefore, the effective fight against bullying and cyberbullying should be considered not only as crime prevention, but also as a national spiritual and educational task.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the effective fight against cyberbullying and its prevention is not the task of any institution or group, but can be carried out through the joint, coordinated actions of the whole society. It is advisable to systematize this process based on the following priority areas:

1. At the parental level:

regular monitoring of children's digital activities, careful observation of their interaction on the Internet;

conducting regular open and trusting dialogue about internet culture, ethical norms, and safe conduct in the digital environment;

application of educational methods aimed at forming in children a sense of empathy, tolerance, responsibility, and self-defense skills.

2. At the level of schools and educational institutions:

Inclusion in the curricula of special lessons, trainings, and seminars covering the topic of cyberbullying;

creation of effectively functioning psychological services, helplines, and consultation centers at educational institutions;

introduction of a system for the early detection, prompt resolution of cases of violence and the adoption of preventive and educational measures against persons who have committed them.

3. In the sphere of legislation and law enforcement:

Clearly define the legal definition of cyberbullying, clarify its types and consequences in legislation;

improvement of mechanisms for interaction with internet platforms to identify aggressors, restrict their activities, and, if necessary, bring them to justice;

Formation of a culture of digital security in society and its wide promotion through the media, education, and enlightenment.

Through the effective implementation of these measures, it will be possible to protect the rights of children and adolescents in the digital environment, ensure their mental stability and social security. After all, cyberbullying is an expression of general culture, legal consciousness, and moral responsibility in society.

References:

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2, Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis of December 29, 2020. <http://president.uz/ru/lists/view/4057>

